

Flexible integrated gasification solid oxide cell (IGSOC) plant for bio-methanol and bio-power generation

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a novel dual-mode flexible integrated gasification solid oxide cell (IGSOC) plant designed to optimize economic performance by switching between methanol production and power generation in response to fluctuating electricity prices. When prices are low, the solid oxide cell (SOC) operates as an electrolyzer (SOEC) to tailor syngas for methanol synthesis; when prices rise, the same stack switches to fuel cell mode (SOFC) to export electricity. The plant integrates biomass drying, a circulating fluidized bed gasifier, syngas cleaning and conditioning, methanol synthesis, and advanced heat recovery systems. Process simulations show that, in methanol mode, a 100 MW_{LHV} biomass-fed plant produces 25.3 tph of methanol, achieving 91 % carbon efficiency and 68.8 % total energy efficiency. In power mode, it delivers 44 MWe net and 1.0 tph of methanol at 49.7 % total efficiency. Techno-economic analysis against historical Danish DK1 electricity price curves yields breakeven methanol selling prices of 554 €/t (2019), 470 €/t (2022), and 727 €/t (2023). These results demonstrate the significant potential of this market-responsive PBtX plant, offering a pathway for renewable fuel and power co-production.

1. Introduction

Bio-methanol (MeOH) and electro-methanol are emerging as a promising solution for the defossilization of the chemical industry as well as of marine transport. Given the limited availability of biomass, it is clear that biomass-based biofuels alone cannot fully meet the demand of sustainable carbon for the chemical industry and for energy carriers [1]. The integration of renewable electricity through electrolysis offers an effective pathway to maximize biogenic carbon utilization via “Power and Biomass-to-X” (PBtX) systems [2–4].

Previous studies have shown that the cost of producing bio/e-fuels through PBtX processes is highly sensitive to electricity prices. Therefore, PBtX processes become economically more competitive if the electrolysis plant can reduce or pause operations during periods of high electricity price [5,6]. This flexibility is essential for optimizing economic performance, as it enables plants to adjust their electricity consumption in response to volatile electricity prices.

The studies that investigated the flexibility for the Power and Biomass-to-Methanol (PBtM) plant are limited. Poluzzi et al. [7]

developed a flexible PBtM process capable of adjusting operations based on the electricity price. The plant is based on sorption-enhanced gasification process and operates in two distinct modes: a “baseline operation”, with no hydrogen addition, and an “enhanced operation” mode, where hydrogen produced via low temperature water electrolysis is added to increase methanol production. When integrated with the Danish electricity market with 2019 price curve, the plant leverages periods of low electricity prices. These low prices are typically driven by high renewable energy generation. During these periods of time, the plant operates the electrolysis unit, producing hydrogen and increasing carbon efficiency from 42.7 % to 68.7 %, while maximizing methanol production. During high-price periods, the electrolysis unit ceases operation, and the plant returns to baseline operation.

The profitability of the flexible PBtM plant is assessed by calculating the Net Present Value (NPV) and the Internal Rate of Return (IRR). For a methanol selling price of 450 €/t, the investment proves unprofitable (negative NPV) when compared to the reference Biomass-to-Methanol plant. However, when the methanol selling price rises to 600 €/t, the economic optimal electrolyzer capacity factor increases to 97.8 %,

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making the PBtM plant competitive, especially with a reduced electrolyzer cost of 400 €/kW. With an electrolyzer capacity factor of 80 % and an electrolyzer cost of 700 €/kW, the levelized cost of methanol is estimated to be around 617 €/t.

A similar study conducted by Poluzzi et al. [6] compares various gasification technologies in a flexible power and biomass-to-methanol plant. In addition to the previously mentioned configuration, they examine processes involving both direct and indirect gasification, where the syngas composition is adjusted by a carbon capture unit and a water-gas shift reactor in the baseline mode, and a low-temperature electrolyzer in the enhanced mode. The carbon efficiency in the enhanced mode increases significantly: from 42.6 % to 90.5 % for the direct O₂-blown gasifier, and from 43.1 % to 67.8 % for the indirect gasifier. Taking into account an 80 % capacity factor for the electrolyzer, with a cost of 700 €/kW and integration into the Danish electricity market in 2019, the leveled cost of methanol is estimated to be 630 €/t for the plant with direct gasifier and 596 €/t for the indirect gasifier. In this study, it was shown that the economic benefit of plant flexibility is highly dependent on electricity market dynamics. For example, with the 2019 Danish price profile, the value of flexible operation remains limited due to the relatively small number of high-price hours. In contrast, under a more volatile price scenario, characterized by a lower average price but more frequent price spikes, a flexible plant would yields 2 to 3 percentage increase in IRR for methanol selling prices between 500 and 550 €/t.

In several studies, not limited to PBtM concepts, reversible solid oxide cells (rSOCs) are utilized to introduce flexibility into integrated chemical processes that produce heat, electricity, and fuels. The core principle is that the flexible SOC can dynamically operate in electrolyzer mode or fuel cell mode depending on resource availability, energy demands, and system profitability. Table 1 summarizes selected studies that explore the role and performance of rSOC-based systems, highlighting their components, flexibility mechanisms, key operational parameters, and associated limitations.

This flexible operation of SOC can also pave the way for enhancing flexibility in Power-to-Biomass-to-Methanol systems. By dynamically switching between electrolysis and fuel cell modes, SOC can balance the intermittent nature of renewable energy inputs with the continuous demands of biomass conversion processes.

For example, in one study on a flexible Power and Biomass-to-Methanol system, Butera et al. [11] present an advanced flexible system that integrates a Two-Stage biomass gasifier and SOC. The plant's design features five operating modes to adapt to fluctuating electricity prices, fundamentally altering its function from an electricity consumer

to a producer. This flexibility is achieved by changing the SOC role and the char gasifier's heating method, which directly impacts the final syngas composition. In Electricity Storage mode, the SOC acts as an electrolysis cell, consuming cheap electricity. As electricity prices rise, the plant can shift to Electricity Heated mode. Here, the SOC functions as an electrically heated reformer, using an alternating current to break down tars without performing electrolysis, which lowers electricity consumption. At higher electricity prices, in the subsequent Electricity Minimum mode, the plant further minimizes power consumption by operating the SOC as a fuel cell to generate the electricity needed for heating the char gasifier, creating a nearly self-sufficient system. Conversely, the Electricity Production modes operate the SOC as an SOFC and use air injection for gasifier heating instead of electricity. Finally, at the highest electricity prices, the Production Plus variant maximizes this by sending all gas to an engine, producing only power. Thermodynamic analysis indicates an input-output efficiency ranging from 70.5 % to 37.0 %, depending on the operating mode. When integrated with the Danish electricity market in 2019, and electrolyzer cost of 250 €/kW (projected for 2050), the levelized cost of methanol is approximately 570 €/t.

In another techno-economic study, Butera et al. [5] investigated the economic competitiveness of flexible methanol production unit [11] against two inflexible, single-mode configurations: a conventional design and an electricity storage design. It should be noted that in both the conventional and electricity storage designs, H₂ from a steam SOEC is added to produce syngas for MeOH production and the electricity storage design includes an electrically heated gasifier. The study calculated the Minimum Fuel Selling Price (MFSP) for methanol across six different electricity price scenarios, finding that the flexible plant's MFSP ranged from 93 to 125 \$/MWh, while the electricity storage and conventional single-mode plants showed ranges of 87–127 \$/MWh and 92–117 \$/MWh, respectively. Despite the operational advantages of the flexible design, the analysis concluded that in most scenarios, flexibility did not translate to superior economic performance. This was primarily attributed to the significantly higher investment cost of the flexible plant (620 M\$) compared to the single-mode plant (390–490 M\$). The study did note, however, that the flexible unit could become the most cost-competitive solution under specific conditions, such as when a "green electricity price limit" was imposed, which severely restricted the operating hours of the single-mode plants.

Previous studies on flexible Power-&-Biomass-to-Methanol (PBtM) plants have either relied on low-temperature electrolyzers that must be periodically shut down [3,4] or on two-stage gasifiers coupled to SOCs. In this study, a novel configuration for a flexible power and

Table 1
Summary of studies utilizing reversible solid oxide cells for flexible energy and chemical production systems.

	Buffo et al. [8]	Zheng et al. [9]	Gu et al. [10]
Assessed process	Power-to-X scheme, converting electricity into hydrogen and heat for multi-sector integration. The rSOC switches between SOEC and SOFC modes based on prioritized energy demand (mobility, electricity, heating).	Power-to-Methanol-to-Power System, converting excess PV electricity into methanol via SOEC-produced syngas. Methanol is stored and reconverted to electricity via SOFC during night or high-price periods, addressing temporal renewable variability.	rSOC-based system, switching between SOEC and SOFC modes. Mode switching depends on electricity demand, prices, hydrogen and heat demand, renewable availability, and energy storage.
Overall System Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - rSOC Plant: 10 MWe SOFC mode; 50 MWe SOEC mode. - Renewable Energy Source: 15 MW wind farm. - Hydrogen Storage - Thermal Storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - rSOC: 1 MW SOEC/SOFC - Renewable Energy Source: 1 MW PV - Thermal Storage: 3500 kWh - Methanol Synthesis: Porous-tube methanol reactor. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - rSOC Plant: 300 MW. - Renewable Energy Sources: 750 MW wind turbines; 1500 MW photovoltaics. - Battery Storage: 150 MWh. - Thermal Storage: 100 MWh. - Hydrogen Storage: 100 tons. - Heat Pump: 50 MW.
Main Takeaways on Flexibility	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The System enables cross-sector decarbonization across transport, power, and heating sectors. 2. Sequential energy prioritization enhances grid stability under variable renewable supply. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Methanol as a liquid energy carrier offers lower storage and transport costs than hydrogen. 2. Dynamic multi-physical modeling is essential to optimize operation under fluctuating PV input. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Bidirectional Flexible Operation model enhances rSOC operational flexibility, reducing system operating costs by 0.81 million CNY compared to static models. 2. Generalized energy storage significantly strengthens system resilience in extreme renewable supply conditions.

biomass-to-methanol plant is explored, building on the concept proposed by Butera et al. [11] and on previous research that focused on integrating a solid oxide electrolysis cell with an oxygen-blown Circulating Fluidized Bed Gasifier (CFBG) by Rajaei et al. [12]. In the latter work, a techno-economic analysis of three configurations has been conducted, involving steam-fed, CO₂-steam-fed, and syngas-fed SOEC. Findings from that work revealed that the type of SOEC and system configuration mildly influence energy efficiency (from 67.04 % to 68.98 %) and carbon efficiency (from 91.06 % to 92.35 %), and all configurations demonstrated comparable overall performance. The syngas-electrolysis configuration achieved the lowest Levelized Cost of Methanol (LCOM) of 560 €/t with average electricity price and electrolyzer cost of 38 €/MWh and 1000 €/kW, respectively.

A key advantage of the syngas-electrolysis approach assessed in Ref. [12] is its ability to maintain the SOC in continuous operation, consistently fed with syngas regardless of the operational modes, which can be SOEC or SOFC.

Accordingly, the proposed flexible plant operates in two distinct modes. In methanol mode, a syngas-fed SOEC optimizes the syngas composition from the gasification process to produce methanol when

electricity prices are low. In power mode, the SOC transitions to SOFC operation, oxidizing clean syngas to generate electricity during periods of high electricity prices. This dual functionality ensures a smooth shift between methanol production and power generation, providing enhanced economic performance and adaptability to fluctuating electricity market conditions.

Starting from the methods and results from Ref. [12], the novelty of this study consists in performing a detailed techno-economic analysis of the integrated gasification solid oxide cell (IGSOC) process, assessing the technical implications of flexible operation and the economic potential of flexibility evaluated under different electricity market price scenarios and different MeOH prices. The main contributions of this study are: (i) a detailed process design and Aspen Plus® simulation of the IGSOC plant operating in methanol and power modes; (ii) mapping of optimal operating mode as a function of electricity and methanol price signals; (iii) techno-economic assessment with calculation of breakeven methanol selling price (BMSP) and other economic indicators under three recent representative electricity market years; (iv) parametric sensitivity analysis on discount rate, SOC cost, biomass and district-heat prices.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the IGSOE plant in a) methanol mode and b) power mode.

2. Plant description

The block diagrams in Fig. 1 (a) and (b) illustrate the flexible Power and Biomass to Methanol plants, designed to operate in two distinct modes. In “methanol mode” (a), the SOC operates as electrolyzer (SOEC), and methanol is the primary product of the plant. In “power mode” (b), the SOC functions as a fuel cell (SOFC), and electricity becomes the primary product of the plant.

The plant operates in two modes, incorporating identical essential conversion stages: biomass drying, gasification, syngas cleaning, SOC, syngas conditioning and compression, methanol synthesis and purification, and the combustion of MeOH loop tail gas in an internal combustion engine. The plant is designed to be fed with 100 MW_{LHV} of woodchips with an initial moisture content of 45 %. The as-received biomass is dried in a belt dryer to reduce its moisture content before being sent to the gasification island. The gasification process is based on a pressurized circulating fluidized bed gasifier (CFBG) that generates syngas at 4 bar and 870 °C.

Following the gasification process, the majority of the carbon input is retained in the syngas as CO, CO₂, CH₄, and C₂H₄, as well as a small amount of tar. A minor fraction of the carbon is removed as unconverted char from the fluidized bed.

The syngas must undergo purification. Initially, it is cleaned to eliminate contaminants like sulfur, chlorine, and ammonia, which could poison the SOC and the downstream catalytic reactor. In the syngas cleaning island, this is achieved using a water scrubber, a liquid Redox “LO-CAT” unit, and activated carbon beds.

In Methanol mode (Fig. 1a), a mixture of preheated steam and syngas at 750 °C is sent to a solid oxide syngas electrolysis cell to co-electrolyze CO₂ and H₂O, producing H₂ and CO, which forms the desired syngas mixture for bio-methanol synthesis. In Power mode (Fig. 1b), it is assumed that 80 % of the clean syngas is combined with steam at 200 °C, preheated, and directed to the SOC, operated as a fuel cell, to generate electricity. The remaining clean syngas is fed to the methanol synthesis loop, assuming that the methanol synthesis process can operate at minimum load with 20 % of the design feed gas.

The methanol synthesis section is fed with gas at 90 bar, obtained by compressing the cleaned and conditioned syngas with a five-stage intercooled compressor. Methanol synthesis is conducted in a conventional tubular boiling water reactor (BWR) with boiling water at 238 °C. The methanol yield per pass is limited by thermodynamic equilibrium, necessitating the recycling of most unconverted reactants back to the reactor. The crude methanol is then cooled to 40 °C and separated from the light gases in a flash unit before being throttled to 2 bar for purification. The purification process utilizes distillation columns to remove light gases from the crude methanol and separate water from methanol.

A cogenerative internal combustion engine (ICE) is used to generate electricity using the purge gases from the methanol synthesis loop and from the methanol purification units.

Furthermore, high-pressure steam generated from the syngas and methanol reactor cooling is expanded in a turbine to produce electricity. The resulting low-pressure steam is directed to the gasifier and the SOC sections. Additionally, low-temperature waste heat can be recovered and sold to the district heating network, if available.

The integrated plant’s mass and energy balances are calculated through process simulations using Aspen Plus®. For thermodynamic properties, the general model used is RKS-BM, complemented with the SRK model in the methanol synthesis section, the NRTL model in the methanol purification section, and the ELECNRTL model in the water scrubber.

The main calculation assumptions are summarized in Table 2. The primary assumptions for the gasification, syngas cleaning, and methanol synthesis units align with the works by Poluzzi et al. [6,13]. Additionally, the SOEC is designed and modeled based on previous similar studies, such as [11,14]. A description of the various plant components and the modeling methods are outlined in the Supplementary

Information. In the following section, the plant operational mode is discussed in more detail.

2.1. Plant operational mode

The flexible power and biomass to methanol plant is designed to optimize its economic performance by adjusting operations based on electricity price fluctuations. When electricity prices are low, the plant operates in methanol mode, leveraging the SOEC’s ability to consume electricity and increase MeOH production. In this mode, the SOEC enables the electrochemical reduction of H₂O and CO₂ into H₂ and CO, enhancing the syngas composition to a desired syngas module ratio for methanol synthesis. The steam-to-carbon (S/C) ratio at the SOEC inlet is adjusted to favor methane reforming and avoid carbon deposition. By using the SOEC to boost syngas conversion, the plant maximizes methanol yield.

Conversely, when electricity prices rise, the plant switches to power mode, and the SOC operates as an SOFC to generate electricity. In this mode, the SOFC oxidizes the syngas, converting chemical energy into electrical power. In this operating mode, it is assumed that 80 % of the syngas is directed to the SOFC after mixing with steam to maintain an appropriate S/C ratio to prevent carbon deposition and ensure stable operation. To further enhance power output, the purge gas from the SOFC is combusted in an ICE. It should be noted that the fuel utilization factor in the SOFC is determined to maximize the power output from both the SOFC and the ICE.

3. Results and discussion

Section 3 consolidates the technical and economic outcomes of this study. Sub-section 3.1 presents the simulation results for both methanol and power modes, including stream properties and performance indicators. Sub-section 3.2 then evaluates economic performance. It begins with an operating-mode map that maximizes hourly marginal revenue, then examines how historical electricity-price distributions affect mode selection and the levelized cost of methanol, and finally concludes with a multi-parameter sensitivity study. Together, these sections provide the quantitative basis for the discussion and conclusions that follow.

3.1. Technical analysis

The outcomes of the process simulations for the plant operating in methanol mode and power mode (illustrated in Fig. 1a and b) are compiled in Tables 3 and 4. These tables provide key properties of the main streams, including temperature, pressure, flow rates, and molar compositions.

Table 5 reports the main results obtained for the SOC in the two operating modes.

To assess the performance of the evaluated power and biomass-to-methanol plants, the following key performance indicators were employed.

Carbon Efficiency (CE): This metric evaluates how effectively a process unit converts the carbon from the input biomass stream into the carbon in the output stream. It is determined as the ratio between the carbon molar flow rate in the methanol product ($F_{C,MeOH}$) and the carbon molar flow rate in the inlet biomass stream ($F_{C,biom}$):

$$CE = \frac{F_{C,MeOH}}{F_{C,biom}} \quad (1)$$

The overall energy efficiency (η_{tot}) is then calculated with Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) for methanol and power operating modes, respectively:

$$\eta_{tot@M} = \frac{(\dot{m}_{MeOH} \cdot LHV_{MeOH})}{(\dot{m}_{biomass} \cdot LHV_{Biomass} + P_{net})} \quad (2)$$

Table 2
Process design parameters.

As-received biomass											
LHV, MJ/kg _{AR}	Moisture, %wt	Proximate analysis, %wt _{dry}		Ultimate analysis, %wt _{dry}							
9.74	45	FC	V	Ash	C	H	N	Cl	S	O	Ash
		18.84	80.0	1.16	51.19	6.08	0.2	0.05	0.02	41.3	1.16
Belt Dryer											
T _{biomass,out} [°C]	80	Moisture at the outlet [wt%]		15							
Gasifier											
T _{Gasifier out} [°C]	870	P _{Gasifier} [bar]		4		S/C [-]		1			
X _{CH4} [kg _{CH4} /kg _{bio, dry}]	0.07	X _{C2H4} [kmol _{C2H4} /kmol _{CH4}]		0.45		Char conversion [%]		95.5			
T _{steam,in} [°C]	400	Sealing gas [kg/kg _{bio, dry}]		H ₂ O = 0.12		Q _{loss} [kW]		1000			
				Air = 0.03							
Syngas cleaning, conditioning and compression											
T _{intercooler,out} [°C]	40	η _{is, comp} [%]		75		η _{mech,scrubber pump} [%]		90			
η _{hyd,scrubber pump} [%]	72	η _{mech, comp} [%]		92		Syngas compressor number of stages		6			
SOC											
P _{SOC} [bar]	3.2	T _{SOECin} [°C]:750		T _{SOECout} [°C]				850		810	
Methanol production											
P [bar]	90	T _{Boiling water} [°C]		238		L _{Tube} [m]		6			
d _{Tube} [mm]	40	ρ _{catalyst} [kg/m ³]		1712		GHSV _{methanol mode} [h ⁻¹]		5000			
d _{catalyst} [mm]	3.5	Bed voidage		0.39		GHSV _{power mode} [h ⁻¹]		1189			
RR _{methanol mode}	4	η _{mech, comp} [%]		94		η _{is, comp} [%]		80			
RR _{power mode}	12										
Methanol purification											
P _{Stabilizing column} [bar]	1.3	Stage number Stabilizing column		20		d _{Stabilizing column} [mm]		0.9			
P _{Concentration column} [bar]	1	Stage number Concentration column		40		d _{Concentration column} [mm]		2.5			
Heat Pump (for concentration column)											
T _{Source} [°C]	64	T _{Sink} [°C]		98		COP _{Real} /COP _{Carnot} [-]		0.5			

$$\eta_{tot@P} = \frac{(\dot{m}_{MeOH} \cdot LHV_{MeOH} + P_{net})}{(\dot{m}_{biomass} \cdot LHV_{Biomass})} \quad (3)$$

Table 6 presents the key results and KPIs of the plant in the two operating modes. In the Methanol mode, the plant prioritizes converting biomass into methanol, achieving a high production rate of 7.03 kg/s (equivalent to 139.9 MW) and a high carbon efficiency of 91.2 %. This mode demands substantial electricity input, particularly for the electrolysis process, which consumes 94.98 MW, leading to a significant net electricity consumption of 104.5 MW. Ultimately, the total energy efficiency in this mode is 68.8 %.

When electricity prices are elevated, the plant can switch to the Power mode, where the focus shifts to electricity generation. In this mode, the plant produces a net electricity output of 43.9 MW, leveraging the energy from the internal combustion engine, fuel cell, and steam turbine. The total energy efficiency in this mode is 49.73 %, i.e. significantly lower than the total efficiency in methanol mode, mostly due to the thermodynamic losses for power generation in the SOFC and the ICE.

Notably, an essential operational strategy involves reserving 20 % of the syngas output to keep the methanol production island continuously operational. This is critical because frequent start-ups and shutdowns of the methanol reactor are impractical and could lead to reduced equipment and catalyst lifetime. Therefore, even when the plant operates in Power mode, methanol production is maintained at a low level, 0.29 kg/s (equivalent to 5.79 MW_{LHV} of methanol output to 3.76 % carbon efficiency), ensuring that the plant can quickly ramp up methanol production when switching back to Methanol mode.

The carbon footprint of methanol is assessed specifically for the methanol production mode, assuming the electricity used is sourced from a low-carbon grid with a carbon intensity of 50 kg_{CO2}/MWh and neglecting other system emissions (e.g. from the biomass supply chain). Under these conditions, the specific emissions for methanol production are 206 kg_{CO2}/t_{MeOH}, which corresponds to 10.4 g_{CO2}/MJ_{lHV}. This result demonstrates a significantly lower carbon footprint compared to conventional fossil-based methanol production routes, which typically range from 30 to 40 g_{CO2}/MJ_{lHV} [15], if low-carbon electricity is used. With an electricity carbon footprint of 150 kg_{CO2}/MWh (i.e. less than the emission factor of most European countries), the carbon footprint of the produced bio/e-methanol would be equivalent to that of fossil methanol.

This operational flexibility allows the plant to optimize its performance based on market conditions, balancing the production of methanol and electricity to maximize profitability while maintaining stable operation of the critical methanol production infrastructure. The ability to switch between modes based on electricity prices not only enhances the plant's economic viability but also provides a strategic advantage in responding to volatile electric markets.

3.2. Economic analysis

The economic analysis is performed using breakeven selling price and levelized cost methods, as explained in the Supplementary Information, where the complete set of assumptions is reported.

Table 7 presents the breakdown of the fixed capital costs for the plant. The analysis uses 2023 euros. As illustrated, the biomass-to-syngas island components, compressors, and SOC are the most capital-intensive sections. Given that the SOC is an immature and capital-intensive technology, a sensitivity analysis is later presented to assess how its cost would impact the economic indicators.

3.2.1. Operational modes determination

The assessed plant functions with the goal of maximizing hourly marginal revenue. For each combination of electricity and methanol prices, a flexible plant can select the mode of operation that yields the highest revenue, as shown in the operating map in Fig. 2, generated based on the following Eq. (4):

$$\begin{aligned} & (\text{MeOH Production}_{\text{MeOH mode}} \times \text{MeOH Price}) \\ & - (\text{Electricity Consumption}_{\text{MeOH mode}} \times \text{Electricity Price}) \\ & = (\text{MeOH Production}_{\text{Power mode}} \times \text{MeOH Price}) \\ & + (\text{Electricity Production}_{\text{Power mode}} \times \text{Electricity Price}) \\ & - (\text{O}_2 \text{ Consumption}_{\text{Power mode}} \times \text{O}_2 \text{ Price}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

It is important to note that we considered no spread between the electricity purchasing and selling prices, for the sake of simplicity. In the presence of such a spread, an electrically balanced intermediate operating mode (i.e. zero electricity import or export) should be considered for prices near the breakeven line between MeOH and Power modes.

Table 3
Stream properties of the assessed plant operating in methanol mode.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
	Biomass Feed	Dried Biomass	Fluidizing Steam	O ₂ to Gasifier	Raw Syngas	Cleaned Syngas	Steam to SOEC	O ₂ from SOEC	Syngas to Compression	Syngas to MeOH synthesis	Recycle Flow	MeOH reactor feed	MeOH to Purification	MeOH product	Light Gas	Purge to ICE
Temperature	25	80	400	25	870	49.77	250	30	30	115	46.81	60.28	41.47	64.58	40	38.25
Pressure	1.01	1.01	5.90	30	3.80	3.2	3.2	3.17	3.07	92	92	92	2	1.01	86.5	1.35
Mass flow rate	10.27	6.64	2.76	1.73	11.95	8	9.22	5.30	11.15	8.5	28.13	36.49	8.07	7.03	28.42	0.47
Mole flow rate	-	-	551	194	2068	1280	1687	596	3243	2687	10,748	13,435	979	790	10,859	133
Mole fraction	-	-	100	-	40.01	3.32	100	-	17.15	-	0.06	0.04	16.87	0.21	0.06	0.05
	-	-	-	-	20.87	33.70	-	-	56.75	68.5	68.91	68.83	0.31	-	68.91	60.12
	-	-	-	-	17.14	27.64	-	-	5.46	6.59	2.27	3.10	0.74	-	2.27	9.28
	-	-	-	-	14.49	23.38	-	-	19.55	23.59	0.98	5.5	0.01	-	0.98	0.88
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.46	0.37	81.31	99.76	0.47	3.38
	-	-	-	-	4.41	7.08	-	-	0.39	0.48	8.7	7.13	0.315	-	8.7	9.69
	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-	1.98	3.13	-	-	0.67	0.81	18.5	14.96	0.13	-	18.5	16.53
	-	-	-	-	1.06	1.71	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.02	-	-
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4
Stream properties of the assessed plant in power mode.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
	Biomass Feed	Dried Biomass	Fluidizing Steam	O ₂ to Gasifier	Raw Syngas	Cleaned Syngas	Syngas to SOFC	Steam to SOFC	SOFC anode exhaust	Syngas to Compression	Syngas to MeOH synthesis	Recycle Flow	MeOH reactor feed	MeOH to Purification	MeOH product	Light Gas	Purge to ICE
Temperature	25	80	348	25	870	48.06	48.06	200	50	48.06	115	45.63	48.93	15	64.55	40	41.79
Pressure	1.01	1.01	5.9	30	3.8	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.1	3.1	92	92	92	2	1.01	86.5	1.35
Mass flow rate	10.27	6.64	2.73	1.73	11.95	7.95	6.36	6.43	14.93	1.57	1.55	26.13	27.68	0.5	0.29	27.18	16.14
Mole flow rate	-	-	546	194	2068	1268	1014	1248	2538	253	245	2949	3195	53	33	3067	2674
Mole fraction	-	-	100	-	40.01	3.09	3.09	100	56.71	3.09	-	0.06	0.05	4.94	0.01	0.06	53.85
	-	-	-	-	20.87	33.83	33.83	-	16.74	33.83	34.66	6.91	9.04	0.09	-	6.91	16.16
	-	-	-	-	17.14	27.67	27.67	-	19.59	27.67	28.65	46.37	45	24.66	-	46.37	21.17
	-	-	-	-	14.49	23.46	23.46	-	6.25	23.46	24.33	21.14	21.38	0.47	-	21.14	6.87
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.98	0.98	0.9	66.96	99.98	0.14	0.14
	-	-	-	-	4.41	7.08	7.08	-	-	7.08	7.34	14.81	14.24	1.08	-	14.81	0.68
	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-	1.98	3.11	3.11	-	-	3.11	3.22	6.04	5.82	-	-	6.04	0.3
	-	-	-	-	1.06	1.72	1.72	-	0.7	1.72	1.78	3.7	3.54	0.07	-	3.69	0.82
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.02	0.01	-	-

Table 5
Main results of the SOC units model in the two operating modes.

	SOEC	SOFC
Feed Mole flow rate (kmole/h)	2967	2299
Feed Composition (% _{mol})		
H ₂ O	58.22	57.21
H ₂	14.54	14.83
CO ₂	11.92	12.26
CO	10.08	10.41
CH ₄	3.05	3.14
C ₂ H ₄	1.35	1.38
N ₂	0.74	0.76
Outlet Mole flow (kmole/h)	3244	2539
Outlet Composition (% _{mol})		
H ₂ O	17.15	56.73
H ₂	56.75	16.7
CO ₂	5.46	19.63
CO	19.55	6.25
CH ₄	0.39	3.12
C ₂ H ₄	–	–
N ₂	0.67	0.7
Input LHV (MW)	87.46	69.5
Output LHV (MW)	176.23	41.03
Current (kA)	63,870	25,560
Area (m ²)	6387	6387
Current density (A/cm ²)	1	0.4
ASR (Ω cm ²)	0.53	0.53
Reversible Voltage (V)	0.95	1.06
Operational Voltage (V)	1.48	0.84
Reactant conversion (%)	62	45
Oxygen through the electrolyte (kg/s)	5.3	2.12
Oxygen Outlet (kg/s)	5.3	–

Table 6
Overall performance of the assessed plant in two modes.

	Methanol mode	Power mode
Inputs		
Biomass input (MW)	100	100
Electric Consumption (MW)		
Electrolysis	94.98	–
Syngas Compressors	10.9	0.96
MeOH Loop Recycle Compressor	0.67	0.14
Heat Pump	2.19	0.11
Dryer	0.65	0.65
Water and Scrubber Pump	0.05	0.07
O ₂ Consumption (kg/s)	–	1.73
Outputs		
MeOH Production (kg/s)	7.03	0.29
O ₂ Production (kg/s)	5.3	–
District Heat (DH) Production (MW)	1.9	6.5
O ₂ net production (kg/s)	3.57	–
Electric Production (MW)		
ICE	4.19	24.05
Steam Turbine	2.07	0.18
SOFC	–	21.64
MeOH output (MW)	139.9	5.79
Total Electricity Consumption (MW)	109.5	1.9
Total Electricity Production (MW)	4.99	45.83
Net Electricity Output (MW)	–104.48	43.92
Carbon Efficiency (%)	91.19	3.76
Total efficiency (%)	68.82	49.73
Total efficiency (%) (with DH)	69.75	56.23
Specific emissions for MeOH production (kg _{CO2} /t _{MeOH})	206 ^a /618 ^b	
Specific emissions for MeOH production (g _{CO2} /MJ _{LHV})	10.4 ^a /31.2 ^b	

^a With an electricity carbon intensity of 50 kg_{CO2}/MWh.

^b With an electricity carbon intensity of 150 kg_{CO2}/MWh.

3.2.2. Impact of the electricity market prices

Fig. 3 shows day-ahead electricity price curves across the years 2019, 2022, and 2023 in the Danish electricity market Zone 1 (DK1), with

Table 7
Breakdown of the fixed capital investment costs.

	Fixed capital investment M€	Share (%)
Components		
Biomass-to-syngas island		
Feedstock handling	11.88	4.17
Belt dryer	9.50	3.33
Pressurized O ₂ CFB gasifier	39.44	13.85
Ceramic hot-gas filter	9.3	3.26
Total	70.12	24.63
Cleaning		
Sulfur removal (Liquid redox)	3.5	1.23
Scrubber	1.67	0.58
Activated carbon	0.44	0.15
Waste water treatment	3.4	1.19
Total	9.01	3.16
SOC	49.38	17.35
Syngas compressors	67.53	23.72
Syngas-to-methanol island		
Methanol reactor	13.95	4.9
Recycle compressor	4.06	1.4
Stabilizing column	0.99	0.34
Concentration column	3.65	1.28
Total	22.65	7.95
Heat Recovery System		
Internal combustion engine	16.04	5.63
Heat Exchangers		
Economizer	0.66	0.23
Evaporator	24.67	8.66
Superheater	0.64	0.22
Other heat exchangers	22.56	7.92
Heat Pump	1.34	0.47
Total	65.91	17.05
Fixed Capital Investment (FCI)	284.6	100
Total Capital Investment (TCI)	334.7	-

distinct characteristics. In 2019, electricity prices were notably stable and low, with the majority of prices clustering around 38 €/MWh, with little fluctuation and very few hours with prices above 100 €/MWh. In 2022, there was a noticeable increase in prices compared to 2019, with average prices of around 219 €/MWh and 80 % of the hours with prices above 100 €/MWh. In 2023, prices were still higher and more volatile than in 2019, but remained lower than in 2022, with an average price of 87 €/MWh and prices above 100 €/MWh for 40 % of the time.

To understand the effect of electricity market price on the operational modes of the IGSO plant, a methanol price of 600 €/t is assumed, which is about 20 % higher than the fossil methanol market price in Europe in 2024 [16] (i.e. this corresponds to a premium price for renewable methanol of about 100 €/t). Fig. 2 indicates that at a 600 €/t methanol selling price, the breakeven electricity price for switching from MeOH to power mode is approximately 100 €/MWh. The dashed lines in Fig. 3 indicate the proportion of electricity price data falling below this threshold, which corresponds to the fraction of time the plant would be operated in methanol production mode. Due to the low electricity prices throughout 2019, the plant would have operated exclusively in methanol mode. In 2022, due to the high average electricity prices, the plant would have operated in methanol mode for only 20 % of the time. In 2023, the plant would have operated with nearly balanced operation between both modes, i.e. about 60 % of the time in methanol mode and 40 % of the time in power mode. These three electricity market prices are used for further economic analyses, including the calculation of NPV (Net Present Value), profitability index (NPV/FCI), IRR (Internal Rate of Return) and payback time.

Fig. 2. Impact of electricity and methanol prices on optimal operating mode and on hourly cash flow.

Fig. 3. Cumulative day-ahead electricity price curve in 2019, 2022 and 2023 in DK1 electricity market zone.

3.2.2.1. Breakeven methanol selling price and levelized cost of methanol. The breakeven methanol selling price (BMSP)¹ required for zero net

¹ In this study, we refer to the breakeven methanol selling price (BMSP) in each considered year as the main methanol cost metric. As a matter of fact, the levelized cost is, by definition, the average selling price over the plant's lifetime that results in a net present value (NPV) of zero. However, since we consider three representative years with different electricity price profiles, the methanol selling price that breakeven with the annual operating costs and capital depreciation is year dependent. If the electricity price distribution is assumed to remain constant throughout the plant's lifetime, the BMSP equals the LCOM.

present value has been calculated in the considered electricity price scenarios and resulted 554 €/t in 2019, 470 €/t in 2022, and 726 €/t in 2023.

It is important to note that in a previous study by the same authors [12], an LCOM of 526 €/t was calculated, based on an average electricity price in year 2019 of 38.49 €/MWh while in this study we obtained a

BMSP in the same year of 554 €/t.² The primary reason for this difference is that this analysis updated the total capital investment to the more recent CEPCI for 2023 instead of 2019, leading to higher costs in this study. Other factors include some changes in the assumptions for the economic analysis and updates in system design and components. For example, while the previous study accounted for operational labor costs as 12.5 % of the operational expenses, including biomass and electricity cost, this study uses higher yearly constant OPEX costs related to the operational labor to reflect the more complex performance of the flexible system. Additionally, larger heat exchangers and internal combustion engines are utilized, enabling power mode operation, which was not considered in the previous study, which assessed an inflexible PBTM plant. On the other hand, a more optimistic long-term assumption for solid oxide cell cost has been assumed, with baseline capital cost of 520 €/kW (in line with long-term targets [17,18]), vs. 1000 €/kW. These conflicting factors result in similar BMSP and LCOM between the two studies for the year 2019.

A comparison of the 2019 BMSP is also made with the study by Butera et al. [5,11], who evaluated a flexible power to methanol system under comparable conditions. Both studies were evaluated using the same 2019 DK1 electricity price and primarily operated in methanol production mode during that year. The two systems also showed comparable carbon efficiencies, 91.2 % in this study and up to 92.3 % in Butera et al.

The BMSP in this study is 554 €/t, compared to the LCOM of 556 \$₂₀₁₉/t in the Butera et al. who assumed a SOC cost of around 280 \$₂₀₁₉/kW. The main reason for this cost difference lies in the difference in total capital investment.

The other economic and operational parameters for the plant are detailed in Table 8. The performance of the flexible system over 2019, 2022, and 2023 reveals significant shifts in operations between methanol and power production modes. In 2019, the system operates in methanol mode for 7884 h/year (99.9 % of the operating time),³ reflecting the low electricity market price in 2019. In 2022, as the electricity price increased significantly, there is a major operational shift towards power mode, which runs for 6669 h/year (84.6 % of the operating time). This change led to a drop in methanol production and a significant decrease in net income from methanol mode. In 2023, the system adjusts again, with a different balance between the two modes. Methanol mode accounted for 6483 h/year (82.2 % of the operating time) and Power mode for 1400 h/year (17.8 % of the operating time).

Table 9 compares the performance of the systems in terms of NPV, IRR, and payback time for methanol prices of 450 €/t, 600 €/t and 800 €/t, assuming fixed electricity price curves of years 2019, 2022, and 2023 throughout the plant's lifetime. When the methanol price is 450 €/t, i.e. aligned with the methanol price in the considered years, the NPV is negative, indicating that the system is not economically competitive with any of the considered electricity price scenarios. With 2019 electricity prices, at a methanol price of 600 €/t, the system achieves an NPV of 106 M€, with an IRR of 9.6 % and a payback time of 12.7 years. When the methanol price increases to 800 €/t, the NPV increases to 564 M€, the IRR more than doubles, and the payback time shortens to 5.1 years,

² It has to be noted that year 2019 featured low electricity prices, that led to methanol mode operation for almost all the year. So, there is no meaningful difference in the operation of a flexible and an inflexible plant, making the BMSP computed in this paper for the flexible IGSO plant methodologically comparable with the LCOM computed in Ref. [12].

³ A capacity factor of 90 % has been assumed for the plants, involving a 7884 total operating hours per year. The considered electricity prices in methanol and power modes used for BMSP are computed as the average electricity prices in the corresponding time shares. For 2019, this means that the electricity price in methanol mode is computed as the average price in the 99.9 % lowest cost hours and the electricity price in power mode is computed as the average price in the 0.1 % highest cost hours.

Table 8

The economic and operational parameters of the IGSO plant to achieve NPV equal to zero.

	2019	2022	2023
Capital Depreciation, M€/y	-29.18	-29.18	-29.18
Fixed OPEX, M€/y	-36.72	-36.72	-36.72
POWER MODE OPERATION			
Hours in power mode, h/y	4 h (0.1 %)	6669 h (84.6 %)	1400 h (17.8 %)
Electricity produced, GWh/y	0.2	293	61.5
Average Electricity Price in power mode €/MWh	104.4	251.6	154.3
Income from electricity sale, M€/y	0.01	73.70	9.46
Methanol Production, t/y	4	6964	1462
Breakeven Methanol Selling Price ^a , €/t	554	47	7237
Income from methanol sale, M€/y	0.00	3.27	1.06
Biomass Cost, M€/y	0.0	-11.27	-2.36
Oxygen Cost, M€/y	0.0	-6.97	-1.46
Net Income, M€/y	0.01	58.73	6.70
METHANOL MODE OPERATION			
Hours in methanol mode, h/y	7879 h (99.9 %)	1214 h (15.4 %)	6483 h (82.2 %)
Electricity consumed, GWh/y	823.2	126.8	677.3
Average Electricity Price in methanol mode €/MWh	38.43	41.12	72.55
Electricity Cost, M€/y	-31.25	-5.21	-48.78
Methanol Production, t/y	199,496	30,915	164,631
Breakeven Methanol Selling Price ^a , €/t	554	470	727
Income from methanol sale, M€/y	110.52	14.44	119.03
Biomass Cost, M€/y	-13.31	-2.06	-10.99
Net Income, M€/y	65.90	7.15	59.27
Net Annual Income ^b , M€/y	29.18	29.18	29.18

^a BMSP, found to make the Net Annual Income equal to the Capital Depreciation.

^b The Net Annual Income is computed as the sum of revenues and costs in power and methanol mode and of the fixed OPEX.

reflecting a significant improvement in profitability. With the 2022 electricity price curve, the financial indicators worsen compared to the 2019 price scenario. With a methanol price of 600 €/t, the NPV drops by 37 %, and the IRR declines to 8.3 %. At 800 €/t, the NPV becomes 202 M€ and the IRR 12.7 %. 2023 electricity price scenario shows a notable downturn at 600 €/t, with the NPV turning negative. However, at 800 €/t, the system achieves an NPV of 144 M€ and an IRR of 11 %, while the payback time remains longer at 11 years. This comparison highlights how methanol prices significantly higher than the recent ones are needed to achieve profitability. It also shows that profitability is increased by both low electricity prices (2019 scenario) and by high electricity prices (2022 scenario), benefiting from either methanol production or power production. The 2023 scenario, featuring intermediate electricity prices, results in lower competitiveness for a given methanol selling price.

3.2.3. Sensitivity analysis

Fig. 4 presents a sensitivity analysis of the BMSP concerning various parameters, including the discount rate (from 5 % to 10 %), biomass price (from 35 €/t to 60 €/t), SOC cost (300 €/kW to 1000 €/kW) and district heating price (from 38 €/MWh to 100 €/MWh), for the electricity price duration curve of year 2023. The analysis explores how variations in these parameters affect the BMSP, expressed as percentage changes. For the discount rate, an increase leads to a significant rise in BMSP, with the highest discount rate (10 %) resulting in a rise of about 8.5 %. Conversely, lowering the discount rate to 5 % slightly reduces the BMSP by almost 2 %. Regarding biomass price, higher prices such as 60 €/t, which is 33 % more than the base cost, cause an increase of 3 % in BMSP. SOC cost, which constitutes 17 % of the plant's fixed capital cost, also plays a crucial role in the BMSP. As the SOC cost decreases from €520/kW to €300/kW, there is a decrease in BMSP of 2 %. In contrast, a SOC

Table 9
Impact of methanol price variations on operating modes and economic KPIs.

	2019			2022			2023		
	450	600	800	450	600	800	450	600	800
MeOH selling price (€/t)	450	600	800	450	600	800	450	600	800
Methanol mode operating time(%)	99.7	99.96	99.99	14.7	21.3	31.4	38.7	67.1	88.3
NPV (M€)	-237	106	564	-8	65	199	-406	-221	144
Profitability Index (NPV/FCI)	-0.7	0.31	1.68	-0.02	0.19	0.6	-1.2	-0.66	0.43
IRR (%)	-	9.6	23.0	-	8.3	12.6	-	-4.5	11.0
Payback time (Years)	-	12.7	5.1	-	14.7	9.7	-	-	11

Fig. 4. A sensitivity analysis of the BMSP by varying (a) SOC cost, (b) Biomass Price, (c) Discount Rate and (d) DH Price. Costs are computed with the electricity price curve of year 2023. Baseline values: SOC cost = 520 €/kW, Biomass price = 45.7 €/t, Discount Rate = 6 %, DH price = 38 €/MWh.

cost of €1000/kW results in an increase of 5 % in BMSP. Regarding the effect of district heating price on the methanol price, as shown in Eq. (4), the revenue generated from selling heat to the district heating network can reduce the BMSP. As an example, by assuming a baseline district heating price of 38 €/MWh, the BMSP would be 626 €/t, which is 1 % lower than the BMSP without revenue from district heating. This also influences the plant’s operational hours, increasing them from 2156 h to 2295 h for Power mode, as the heat produced is approximately 4.6 MW higher in Power mode compared to Methanol mode. However, since the revenue from district heating is relatively small, even when the price increases from 38 €/MWh to 100 €/MWh, the BMSP decreases by only 1 %.

Overall, the figure demonstrates that the discount rate and SOC cost have the most significant impact on BMSP.

As mentioned before, MeOH price plays a significant role in determining the operational mode of the IGSO plant and other economic indicators such as NPV or Profitability Index (NPV to FCI ratio), IRR and payback time. Fig. 5 shows the impact of varying methanol prices and reveals significant trends across these financial parameters. As the MeOH price increases from 500 €/t to 1000 €/t, the percentage of hours spent in Methanol mode roughly doubles in the years 2022 and 2023.

Consequently, there is a notable rise in Profitability Index in the year 2019 and 2023 scenarios, which escalates from approximately -0.3/-0.2 to around 1.8/3.0. In the year 2022 scenario, as the system mostly works in power mode, the Profitability Index is less sensitive to the MeOH price. Concurrently, the payback time experiences a dramatic reduction, especially in year 2023 scenario. Similarly, the IRR shows substantial growth, starting from near 0 % at the lower MeOH price and reaching about 30 %, 15 %, and 20 % at the higher end in 2019, 2022 and 2023, respectively. These findings illustrate that higher MeOH prices substantially enhance the economic performance of the plant.

4. Limitations of the study and recommendations

The results of this study demonstrate that producing bio-methanol and bio-power in flexible integrated gasification solid oxide cell (IGSO) plants is energetically and environmentally sound and can be economically competitive in economic scenarios with high bio/e-methanol market price and high electricity price volatility. However, the analysis presented in this paper is based on a set of simplifying assumptions that limit its general applicability and highlight avenues for further research. Key limitations of the current assessment include:

Fig. 5. The economic impact of varying methanol prices on a) Profitability Index, b) Payback time, c) IRR and d) operational mode. For the calculation of these economic indicators, it is assumed that the electricity price profiles remain constant throughout the plant's lifetime and are identical to those of the considered year.

- **Plant transients:** although real-world facilities are subject to thermal and mechanical constraints that limit both the frequency and the rate of transition between operating modes, the techno-economic analysis assumes unrestricted flexibility in mode switching.
- **Methanol loop shutdown rate:** for power mode operation, we assumed a minimum feed of 20 % of the nominal flow rate. This assumption needs to be validated experimentally or with more detailed components modelling.
- **SOC technology:** the study does not address the specifics of reversible SOC units working on syngas feed with flexibility requirements. Experimental validation is still needed regarding materials selection, performance degradation and operational flexibility.
- **Electricity pricing and operational dynamics:** power costs are represented using cumulative duration price curves. This approach overlooks intraday price fluctuations, start-up sequences, ramp-rate constraints, thermal inertia, and cycling-induced degradation. Such constraints may force the IGSO plant to operate in sub-optimal mode in some periods of the year. Yearly simulations with at least hourly discretization should be conducted in future studies, combining electricity prices with the plant's dynamic constraints.

5. Conclusions

This study introduces a novel dual-mode flexible integrated gasification solid oxide cell (IGSO) plant, designed to optimize economic performance through its ability to switch between methanol production and power generation. Key components of the plant include a biomass drying system, a circulating fluidized bed gasifier, syngas cleaning and conditioning units, methanol synthesis, and integrated heat recovery systems. Utilizing a solid oxide cell working as both an electrolyzer in methanol mode and a fuel cell in power mode, the system adapts to fluctuating electricity prices, maximizing methanol yield during low-price periods and producing electricity during high-price periods. This flexibility enhances operational efficiency and aligns with evolving energy market dynamics. The key results of this study are summarized as follows:

- In methanol mode, the system can achieve a production rate of 25.3 tph with a carbon efficiency of 91.2 % and an overall energy efficiency of 68.8 %, which increased to 69.7 % with district heating. In power mode, the system can deliver a net electricity output of 43.9 MW and a methanol production of 1.0 tph, with a carbon efficiency of 3.8 % and an energy efficiency of 49.7 %, improving to 56.2 % with district heating.
- The breakeven methanol selling price (BMSPP) has been computed under different electricity price scenarios from the Danish DK1 market in the years 2019, 2022, and 2023. In the 2019 price scenario, characterized by low and stable electricity prices (38 €/MWh on average) a BMSPP of 554 €/t was calculated. In the 2022 scenario, the BMSPP decreased to 470 €/t as electricity prices increased to an average of 219 €/MWh. This led to more frequent operation and greater profits in power mode. In the 2023 electricity price scenario, BMSPP rose to 727 €/t, driven by an electricity market with intermediate electricity prices (87 €/MWh on average), leading to moderate economic benefits from both electricity consumption for increased methanol production and from power generation.
- Economic metrics at a methanol selling price of 800 €/t resulted in an IRR of 23 % in 2019, 12.7 % in 2022, and 11.1 % in 2023, reflecting the significant impact of electricity prices on the project's financial performance and showing that profitability is increased by both low electricity prices (2019 scenario) and by high electricity prices (2022 scenario), benefiting from the either methanol production or power production.
- Sensitivity analysis showed that varying the SOC cost between 300 €/kW and 1000 €/kW resulted in 8 % variation in BMSPP, highlighting the fairly low economic impact of the SOC technology cost on the economic indicators.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Fatemeh Rajaei: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Matteo C. Romano:** Writing –

review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jouni Ritvanen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2025.138457>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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